

Existence of Life after Death: A Jain Perspective

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Jainism is the oldest religion in Indian continent. It emphasizes duality of existence, namely *jîva*/sentient beings and *ajîva*/insentient being. There are infinite independent sentient beings (called as empirical or *samsâri* soul), each with its own soul, in this cosmos. Each soul is active and capable of achieving the supreme soul (*paramâtmana*) state.

The empirical soul is defiled with karmic impurities which cause its transmigration through cycles of birth-death-birth till the empirical soul purges all its *kârmika* impurities associated to become supreme soul and exit the transmigration cycle.

Indian as well as Western scholars have already dealt the passionate question what are the possibilities after death and what are the experiences? Many people have reported near death experiences, what do they mean and what happens when die?

The experimental method, useful for scientific question, is inadequate for evaluating near death experiences. It is impossible in medical emergencies to establish the required controlled situations and repeatability. Scientists also have no mind-reading machines to evaluate mental/spiritual experiences. And finding volunteers for near death experiments would be difficult. Some suggest a spiritual method for evaluating these phenomena. What if we could find a spiritual authority, someone with trustworthy credentials, to tell us the truth about after life issues?¹

These all issues are discussed in Indian philosophies as well as Jainism. First we have to think of the concept of soul in Jainism then we understand what the life is after death.

Jain beliefs about the soul

Jain ideas about the soul differ from those of many other religions. The Jain word that comes closest to soul is *jîva*, which means a conscious, living being. For Jains body and soul are different things: the body is just an inanimate container - the conscious being is the *jîva*. After each bodily death, the *jîva* is reborn into a different body to live another life, until it achieves liberation. When a *jîva* is embodied (i.e. in a body), it exists throughout that body and isn't found in any particular bit of it.

Jains believe²:

- The soul exists forever.
- Each soul is always independent.
- The soul is responsible for what it does.
- The soul experiences the consequences of its actions.
- The soul can become liberated from the cycle of birth and death.
- Not all souls can be liberated - some souls are inherently incapable of achieving this.
- The soul can evolve towards that liberation by following principles of behaviour.

Individuality

Each *jîva* is an individual quite independent of other *jîvas*. This is different from one of the Hindu Vedanta schools of belief where each soul is part of a single ultimate reality.

Jains believe that there are an infinite number of souls in the universe - every living thing, no matter how primitive, is a *jîva* - and at any given time many of these *jîvas* are not embodied.

Souls have not fallen from perfection

For Jains, each *jīva* has been associated with matter, and involved in the cycle of birth and death since the beginning of time. They did not in some way fall from perfection to become involved in this cycle.

Some *jīvas*, through their own efforts, have become liberated and escaped from the cycle.

Liberated souls³

Some *jīvas* have achieved liberation from the cycle of *samsāra* or reincarnation and are not reborn. They are called siddhas.

Liberated *jīvas* don't have physical bodies; they possess infinite knowledge, infinite vision, infinite power, and infinite bliss - in effect they have become perfect beings.

This makes liberated *jīvas* the beings most like gods in Jain belief, but they are very different from the conventional idea of gods:

- They do not create or destroy.
- It's not possible to have any sort of relationship with them.
- They do not intervene in the universe.
- They did not set down the laws of the universe.
- They do not make any demands on human beings.
- They don't reward human beings in any way, or forgive their sins, or give them grace.
- Human beings don't owe their existence to them.
- Humans can only use them as an inspiration.

So when Jains worship 'gods' they do so to set before themselves the example of perfection that they want to follow in their own lives.

Non-liberated souls⁴

Every *jīva* has the possibility of achieving liberation, and thus of becoming a god, and each soul is involved in a process of evolving towards that state.

Categories of non-liberated soul

Ekendriya - beings with one sense

Jains include many things as *jīvas* that non-Jains regard as either inanimate or plants. They classify these as immobile beings, with only one sense - the sense of touch:

- Earth-bodied: clay, sand, metal etc.
- Water-bodied: fog, rain, ice etc.
- Fire-bodied: fire, lightning etc.
- Air-bodied: wind, gas etc.
- Plant-bodied: trees, flowers, vegetables etc.

Dvindriya - beings with two senses

These are very simple organisms that are thought to have two senses - touch and taste. This category includes things like worms and termites.

Treindriya - beings with three senses

These have the senses of touch, taste and smell. This category includes insects like ants, beetles and moths.

Caurindriya - beings with four senses

These have the senses of touch, taste, smell and sight. This category includes wasps, locusts and scorpions.

Pañcendriya - beings with five senses

These have the senses of touch, taste, smell, sight and hearing. There are four classes of these beings:

- Infernal beings: souls living in hell. This form of *jīva* experiences the greatest suffering.
- Higher animals: This includes all non-human animals above insects.
- Human beings: This is the only form of *jīva* which is able to obtain liberation directly.

- Heavenly beings: This form of *jîva* is the happiest.

The above classification related to *jîva* and their attributes who emphasize the existence of life as long time as they appear. The most important issue is the life after death. I think in my mind, it is based on doctrine of karma. *Because when the jîva associated with karmic particle they subjugated the life.* Jain philosophy therefore goes to great length to describe its unique karma doctrine, it follows that the state of the soul at any given time is due to the *Karma* accumulated over countless ages. However, the Jain doctrine of *Karma* is distinctive. *Karma* is a unique concept of Jains. *Karma* is a complexity of material particles bonded with the soul and infecting its nature. The fine matter particles called *pudgala* (known as *kârmaṇa vargaṇâs* in Jainism), which can become karma, fills the entire cosmos. An empirical soul does some activity (called *bhâva* karma or psychic activities), as a result of its energy (*vîrya*) quality. These activities through the faculties of mind, body and speech affect subtle matter particles (*kârmaṇa vargaṇâs*), which get attracted towards the space points of the soul and then form harmony with them. All the *karma* theory caused of birth and death cycle and it depicted in Jain *âgamas*. According to *karma* doctrine, the life after death exists. Its existence is based on the activities of mind, body and speech in this and earlier lives stored as *karmas* particles with the empirical soul. There are eight primary species of matter *karmas*. The important species out of the eight primary species for the current essay is *Nâma* or physique making *karma* with 93 sub species.

To better understand *Karma* doctrine to show there is life after death, in this paper deal some certain and important topics, which as follow-

1. Concept of *Âyus-Karma* which confers on a being a certain quantum of life in one of the four states of existence.
2. Discuss in detail of *tîrthaṅkaras* birth cycle to show there is life after death at achieve the liberation.

3. Discuss some stories depicted in *âgamic* text *Vipâka-Sûtra* that tend to show life after death in certain manner. Now we discuss one by one topic.

The *Âyus-Karma* confers on a being a certain quantum of life in one of the 4 states of existence. One therefore distinguishes:

- I. *deva-âyus*, the celestial *âyus*,
- II. *manuṣya-âyus*, the human *âyus*,
- III. *tiryag-âyus*, the animal *âyus*,
- IV. *nâraka-âyus*, the infernal *âyus*

The âyus-karma bestows a certain quantity to life, but not a definite number of years of life. For as with a sponge, the quantity of water that it absorbs is determined, but not the time it takes to leave it, so also the quantum of life is determined, but not the time occupied in its consumption. The word *âyus* would, therefore be approximately interpreted by “quantity of vitality”; but it is better to leave it untranslated as a *terminus technicus*. The *âyus* of the new existence is always bound during the life immediately preceding it, especially in the 3rd, 9th or 27th part or within the last 48 minutes of it.⁵

The *âyus-karma* is divided to *deva*, *manuṣya*, *tiryag* and *nâraka gati*, so it is very important to discuss to carry the birth after life and it is the continuous process. This karma is describe how long the life of the *jîva* and primary it is the cause to take life after birth. Hence, every *karma* is determined to new birth and shows there is life after birth.

My aim to discuss the *Âyus karma* is to show these all *karma* is not only for the present life but also carry to next birth. The *âyus-karma* is to be determined by previous birth or past life of the *jîva*. If we think that there is no life after death, then the theory is in vain.

Now we discussed the second point detail of *tīrthaṅkaras* birth cycle to show there is life after death at achieve the liberation. We know that the birth of *tīrthaṅkaras* is not only in the present life but also the result of some previous life. The *Kalpasūtra* starts the narration of the life of *Bhagavāna Mahāvīra*. But the explanatory scriptures and commentaries contain interesting details of the gradual spiritual; evolution of the soul through twenty six earlier incarnations. Significant events from these earlier incarnations have been presented. Here I mention some stories that depict that there is life after death of Mahāvīra. The stories are as follow

1. Nāyasāra⁶: The twenty seventh birth before being born as *Bhagavāna Mahāvīra*, this soul was a forester working for king Shatrumardan of Pratisthan city in the west Mahāvīdeh area. He used to bring all the wood required for construction purposes from the forest. One day at noon time all the workers were taking rest after their lunch. *Nāyasāra* also sat under a tree in order to take the food he had brought along. Before starting to eat he saw some ascetics wandering at the foot of nearby hills. *Nāyasāra* thought that these ascetics are wandering without food or water in this scorching sun. If they happen to come this side, I will offer a part of my food to them. I will be benefitted by this simple act of serving guests and my day will become purposeful.

Innocent *Nāyasāra* waited looking at the approaching ascetics. With deep devotion he offered them his pure food. When they proceeded towards the town, *Nāyasāra* accompanied them for some distance to show the way. When *Nāyasāra* bowed before the ascetics before taking their leave, they gave him sermons of the true path. Devoted and respectful, *Nāyasāra* got enlightened and the seed of righteousness (*Samyaktva*) sprouted in his mind. As this is the starting point of spiritual evolution, the counting of the earlier incarnations of the soul that became *Bhagavāna Mahāvīra* begins here.

2. Marichi⁷

After completing his age (the age of a being, according to Jainism, is a fixed period determined by actions in the immediately preceding birth), the soul of *Nāyasāra* was reborn as a god in the Saudharma kalpa. He then took birth as Marichi, the son of Chakravarti (sovereign of six continents) Bharat in the city of Ayodhya. After hearing the first discourse of *Bhagavāna R̥ṣabhadeva* he became a *aramaṇa*. But as he could not sustain the rigorous ascetic codes, he abandoned the dress of a *aramaṇa* and became a Tridandi Parivrajak (a class of mendicants). According to the Jain tradition, Marichi was the founder of the *Parivrājaka* School. The soul of Marichi moved from the human dimension to that of gods and back again for many incarnations. When born as human he became *Parivrājaka* many a time and observed numerous austerities. In his nineteenth incarnation he became Triprishtha Vasudeva.

3. The Poison of Bloated Ego: *Tṛpṛṣṭa Vāsudeva*⁸

Queen Mrigavati of King Prajapati of Potanpur gave birth to an extremely powerful son. He was named *Tṛpṛṣṭa*. One day Ashvagriva sent an order to Prajapati, “A ferocious lion has created havoc in the Shali area. Immediately proceed to that area and protect the farmers from the lion

Tṛpṛṣṭa and his elder brother Baldeva Achala Kumar went to that forest and enquired about the lion from the local populace. He caught hold of the mouth of the lion and tore it apart. Standing at a safe distance, the farmers jumped with joy and hailed the prince. The driver of the chariot of the prince went near the writhing lion, said a few words of sympathy, and covered its wounds- with medicinal herbs. The dying moments of the beast became peaceful. This act infused a feeling of affection for the driver in the mind of the dying lion.

When the driver reincarnated as the chief disciple of *Bhagavāna Mahāvīra*, Indrabhuti Gautam, this lion was born as a farmer. Prince *Tṛpṛṣṭa* conquered the evil king Prativāsudev Ashwagrīva and

established his own empire over three continents. He became the first Vāsudeva of this cycle of time.

The Right Direction: Priyamitra Chakravati⁹

After seeing many auspicious dreams, the queen of Dhananjaya, the ruler of Mukanagari, gave birth to a son. He was named Priyamitra. As a result of the virtuous karmas and his bravery he conquered all the six continents and became a Chakravarti. He enjoyed all the pleasures and grandeur befitting a Chakravarti. In the end of he obtained detachment and became a *Āramaṇa* by taking *dikṣā*. (for formal act of renouncing the mundane life-style) from Pottilacharya. Living his age, he was reborn as a god in the *Mahāsūkra-kalpa* from where, in the next incarnation, he was born as the son of king Jitshatru of Chaharangari.

Austere Practices: Nandan Muni¹⁰

The life of prince Nandan (son of king Jitshatru) was like a lotus flower in the swamp of passions and mundane indulgences. The attraction of the beauty and love of beautiful damsels did not divert him from his spiritual quest. Finally he became a disciple of Pottilacharya. Becoming an ascetic, he started purifying his soul with the fire of penance. He undertook the tough practice of the twenty-step penance that includes discipline, penance, devotion for Arihant, service of the ascetic, and other such purifying acts. As a result of these practices, he earned the *tīrthaṅkara-nāma-karma-gotra-karma* (the karma that would make him a *tīrthaṅkara* in a future birth). He spent about a hundred thousand years as a *āramaṇa* with perfect discipline, he reincarnated as a god in the *Pranat Pushpottar Viman* (a specific dimension of gods). This was the birth preceding his reincarnation as Mahāvīra.

Tīrthaṅkara Mahāvīra¹¹

The next birth of Nandan Muni is *tīrthaṅkara* Mahāvīra. The birth of Mahāvīra travelled so many life and death year, and then born as *tīrthaṅkara*. The most important thing of this life is this one is last and

final birth of this soul. I am emphasising these all points to show there is life after death whenever we illuminate the cycle of karma. Lord Mahavir was the twenty-fourth and the last *tīrthaṅkara* of the Jain religion. According to Jain philosophy, all *tīrthaṅkaras* were born as human beings but they have attained a state of perfection or enlightenment through meditation and self realization. Mahāvīra spent his next twelve years in deep silence and meditation to conquer his desires and feelings. He went without food for long periods. He carefully avoided harming or annoying other living beings including animals, birds, and plants. His ways of meditation, days of austerities, and mode of behaviour furnish a beautiful example for monks and nuns in religious life. His spiritual pursuit lasted for twelve years. At the end he realized perfect perception, knowledge, power, and bliss. This realization is known as *kevala-jñāna*. He spent the next thirty years travelling on bare feet around India preaching to the people the eternal truth he realized. He attracted people from all walks of life, rich and poor, kings and commoners, men and women, princes and priests, touchable and untouchables. He organized his followers, into a fourfold order, namely monk (*Sādhu*), nun (*Sādhvi*), layman (*śrāvaka*), and laywoman (*śrāvikā*). Later on they are known as Jains. The ultimate objective of his teaching is how one can attain the total freedom from the cycle of birth, life, pain, misery, and death, and achieve the permanent blissful state of one's self. This is also known as liberation, *nirvāṇa*, absolute freedom, or *Mokṣa*. He explained that from eternity, every living being (soul) is in bondage of karmic atoms that are accumulated by its own good or bad deeds. Under the influence of *karma*, the soul is habituated to seek pleasures in materialistic belongings and possessions which are the deep rooted causes of self-cantered violent thoughts, deeds, anger, hatred, greed, and such other vices. These result in accumulating more karma.

These all birth of *tīrthaṅkaras* shows there is always life after death till the karmas decay. If we do not accept the life after death then we never systemise the life cycle of Mahāvīra till omniscient, because

every life is related to previous life, this is the chain of life and death. When we illuminate this circle we do not come find the worldly life.

Now we discussed the third point in which detail of some stories depicted in Jain agamas especially in *Vipāk sūtra*. In *Vipāk sūtra* there are two major chapters (*arutaskandhas*) namely *Duḥkha Vipāk* and *Sukha Vipāk*. In *Duḥkha Vipāk* there are ten stories related to their past *karmas* and proved life after death in certain manner. The stories related to the 10 different persons who were suffering from their past *karmas*. I am giving some stories in short:

1. Mṛgaputra

Since Mṛgaputra birth that he was blind, dumb and deaf, crippled and was with *hund-saṁsthān* (crooked constitution; a body constitution where almost every part of body is deformed and disfigured). He suffered from congenital rheumatism (*vaat-roag*). That child had no hands, feet, ears or nose. He only had mere outlines of these parts and those too for namesake. Therefore, that Mṛga Devi was feeding and bringing up that child under wraps in a secret cellar. The past birth of Mṛgaputra is as follow. A king named Dhanapati was the ruler of that city. In that borough there was a governor (*rashtakoot*) named Ekadi (Ikkai) who was irreligious and dushprtyanandi (a person who enjoys evil deeds or who is so discontented that it is difficult to please him). That governor Ekadi ruled and protected the five hundred villages of Vijayavardhaman borough. He would take back twice of whatever grains he gave to farmers. He took bribe and tortured the people ruthlessly. He charged excessive interest from them and charged them of murder and other crimes. He extorted money from people and appointed agents at various places for collecting such funds. He nurtured and protected thieves and other rogues. He would set fire to villages, torment and rob travellers. This way he continued to exploit and torment people. He had imposed his tortuous rule by whipping people, impoverishing them and forcing them to go against religion. The present birth of Mṛgaputra is the result of previous birth of

Ekadi. If we think there is no birth then how it will prove that Mṛgaputra is the Ekardi in –previous birth.

2. Ujjhitaka: The story of Ujjhitak Kumar describing the grave consequences of sinful deeds like cruel, tortuous, and violent treatment of animals; extreme lust and adultery. These stories also reveal that when such sinful being is conceived, the mother has equally base and violent *dohad* (desires of a pregnant mother). Such *dohad* is said to be the indicator of the eventual attitude of the being to be born.

3. Abhagnasen: The story of Abhagnasen is consequences or fruits of stealing, looting, violence, murder and other such cruel and criminal acts committed by him, the villainous leader of thieves, are narrated. It is noteworthy that in his previous birth he was a prominent trader of eggs. He was a gourmand and in order to satiate his taste buds he killed animals and ate meat besides trading in eggs, meat and wine. When such sinner was conceived, his mother too had desire of killing animals and consuming meat and wine during her pregnancy. This vivid dreadful description of Abhagnasen's plight, followed by the details of his passage through base genuses like hell and animal for numerous cycles of rebirth, gives inspiration to avoid evil deeds.

4. Shakat: This story lucidly details the agonising consequences of cruelty to animals and non-vegetarianism. Although a butcher by profession, Chhannik enjoys killing animals and eating meat. He also indulges in lascivious activities and adultery. He gravely suffers the consequences for many births.

5. Bṛhaspatidatta: The story of Bṛhaspatidatta informs about the grave consequences and bitter fruits of cruelty, sinful activity, and adultery. Even though Bṛhaspatidatt was the state priest, he deceived his friend, the king, and indulged in adultery with the queen. He not only got harsh punishment for this evil deed during the same life time but he had to suffer the consequences of many other violent and sinful deeds, committed during this and many past births, for millions of rebirths. This chapter contain shair-raising description of that.

6. Nandivardhan: The story of Nandivardhan is the heart-rending description of the pathetic and horrific condition of prince Nandivardhan (Nandishena). During this birth Nandivardhan goes against his father and wants to gain the kingdom by killing his father. He is being punished by the guards for this only. But at the root of this entire are the bad *karmas* acquired during the past birth, when he was Duryodhan, the jailer. The duty of a jailer is to protect people from rogues and tyrants and subdue evil. But when that protector, bereft of humanity, transforms into a demon and employs a ruthless and pitiless punitive policy that puts even demons to shame, he disgraces his post as well as humanity. The extremely harsh system of punishment adopted by Duryodhan has been described in details in a hair-raising style by the author of this *Āgama*. Shivers go through the spine while reading or listening to it. This story describes the fruits of these cruel and ruthless evil acts. This description reveals the meanest point of the harsh ancient system of punishment.

7. Umbardatta: The story of Umbardatta informs about the grave consequences and bitter fruits of violent and cruel deeds committed during the past birth. However, there is a variation in the theme of this story.

8. Shaurikadatt: This eighth chapter describes a particular violent profession and its bitter fruits. It is more relevant in modern times. The central theme of this chapter is to describe the bitter fruits of sale and consumption of meat. Shriyak the cook killed or arranged to get killed a variety of animals and birds and prepared food for his master, the king. He too ate that food. As a result of this violence inspiring karma-programming he takes rebirth as Shaurikadatt Fisherman. He becomes a big fish-merchant. In order to catch fish he even poisons and dries ponds and lakes. This way, employing extremely cruel means, he indulges in fish-trading. He develops an insatiable craving for non-vegetarian diet. He suffers bitter fruits of this act during this life and continues to suffer miserable consequences

for many future births. This explicates that not only the meat eater but also the cook, the seller, and the provider of meat is equally responsible for the violence involved.

9. Devadattaa: This ninth story contains the horrifying story of a cruel woman. The preceding story contained the description of callous male characters that killed and tortured animals, birds, and fish; but this story describes a female character that mercilessly kills her own mother-in-law. In her earlier birth she was king Simhasen, a male. Instigated by his chief queen he imprisons the mothers of his other four hundred wives in a camouflaged house through deception and then burns them alive while they were asleep. The perpetrator of such cruel deed dies with cruel attitude and reincarnates as girl Devadatta. Although endowed with physical beauty, Devadatta had a perverted, ugly, and despicable mind. For her unrestricted enjoyment of mundane pleasures she mercilessly killed the mother of his husband, a devotee of his mother.

10. Anjoo: This story narrates the bitter fruits of unchecked licentious activities of a corrupt woman. This is a brief but effective story providing inspiration to avoid lechery.

These all stories shows that there is life after death because each story has their own past *karmas* and this present birth depicted there is life after destroy the body. Entire Jainism we have found so many scriptures and story to provoke to proof there is existence of life after the concept of death.

Conclusion

Jain doctrine of soul and karma do shed credible light on life after death. Its canonical and story literature is full of life sketches of its auspicious persons as well as common livings, even the belonging to animal, heavenly and hellish beings living life after their death. This cycle of birth-death-birth is called *samsāra* and is wrought with sufferings as birth denotes total dependence on others for everything and unknown while death denotes unknown and separation. Their

doctrine of karma, particularly the *Nāma* and species along with *Āyus* their secondary species, give details of the journey of soul through various destinies (i.e. births and deaths in different states) and how the soul can come out of this cycle of transmigration to attain a state of perfection i.e. moksha where there is no death and the soul in its pure form enjoys a state of bliss and knowledge eternally i.e. *sat-cit-ānanda*.

References

1. Article on One Minute after Death By Rusty Wright,
2. *Sarvārtha Siddhi* 5/19, *Syādvāda Mañjari* 7, *Syādvāda Mañjari* 17, *Āpta Mīmāṃsā* 84, *Syādvāda Mañjari* 17
3. *Dravya Saṁgraha*, Ācārya Nemi Candra Sindhanta Deva
4. *Ācārya Tulsi, Āyāro*, -1/176, Jain Vishwa Bharti Ladnun, (Raj.)
5. Glesenapp, H.P., *Doctrine of Karman in Jain Philosophy*, p. 11, P.V. Research Institute, Varanasi-05
6. *Illustrated Shri Kalpasutra*, Pravartak Shri Amar Muni, Padma Prakashan, Padma Dham, Narela mandī, Delhi, 2008, p. 9
7. Ibid, p. 9
8. Ibid, p. 10
9. Ibid, p. 11
10. Ibid, p. 12
11. Ibid, p. 12-40
12. *Vipāk Sūtra*, Convenor & Founder Editor- Yuvacharya Shri Mishrimalji Maharaj 'Madhukar', Editor Shobha chandra Bharill, Shri Agam Prakashan Samiti, Beawar, 2012, p. 18-19

Bibliography

- *Vipāk Sūtra*, Ed. Yuvācārya Madhukar Muni, Shri Agam Prakashan Samiti, Vyavar (Raj.), 2012
- *Illustrated Shri Kalpasūtra*, Pravartak Shri Amar Muni, Padma Prakashan, Padma dham, Narela Mandi, Delhi, 2008
- Glasenapp, H. V., *Doctrine of Karman in Jain Philosophy*, P.V. Research Institute, Varanasi, 1991
- *Jain Dharma Paricaya*, Ed. Vrishabh Prasad Jain, Bhartiya Jnanapeeth, Delhi, 2014
- Weiss, Brian, *Many lives, Many Masters*, Piatkus An imprint of little, Brown Book Group, 100 Victoria Embankment, London
- *Vipāk Sūtra*, Compiled by Muni Deepratnasagar, Jain Aagam (English) On Line Series
- Study Notes of International School for Jain Studies
- Mehta, Molahalal, *Jain Dharma Darshan: Ek Samik śātmaka Parichay*, Seth Mutha Chhaganamal Memorial foundation, Bangalore.
- Bhaskar, Bhag Chand, *Jainism and Mahavira*, Shri Digambar Publication.